

**On the Physico-chemical Properties of Electrolysed
Gels of Silica, Alumina, Ferric Hydroxide and
their Mixtures. Part II. Moisture Retention
Capacity of the Gels Saturated with
Different Cations.**

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In a previous paper of this series (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1936, **13**, 204) the ion exchange properties of the above synthetic gels, which are probable constituents of soil, have been described. In the present investigation their property of absorbing and retaining water vapour under conditions of varying aqueous tensions, have been studied. The results have a bearing on the property of moisture retention by soil colloids, a subject which has evoked considerable interest in recent years. Notable contributions in this direction have been made, amongst others, by Anderson (*J. Agric. Res.*, 1929, **38**, 565), Puri, Crowther and Keen (*J. Agric. Sci.*, 1925, **15**, 86), Parker and Pate (*J. Amer. Soc. Agron.*, 1926, **18**, 470), Thomas (*Soil Sci.*, 1928, **25**, 485) and Bayer (*J. Amer. Soc. Agron.*, 1928, **20**, 921).

The property of silica gel to absorb water vapour is well known. The recent investigations of Urquhart (*J. Textile Inst.*, 1929, **20**, 117), Lambert (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1931, **A134**, 246) and Pidgeon (*Canadian J. Res.*, 1934, **10**, 713) have definitely established a hysteresis effect characterising the phenomenon. Puri, Crowther and Keen (*loc. cit.*) obtained evidence of a similar hysteresis effect in the case of soil colloids. Under the experimental conditions of this work it has not been possible to study the nature of the hysteresis loop, the main object of this investigation being to study the variation of the moisture retention capacity of the gels depending on their composition and the nature of the cations saturating them.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

The methods of preparing the gels and saturating them with various cations have been described in the previous part (*loc. cit.*).

The following sulphuric acid-water mixtures were prepared to

correspond to different V. P. (extrapolated from the figures given in Landolt Börnstein Tabellen, 5 Auflage II, p. 1935).

Temp. 34°.					
	1	2	3	4	5
Acid (%) ...	23.0	42.0	55.8	62.2	81.1
V. P. (mm.) ...	33.63	21.38	10.25	6.20	0.55

Five desiccators, each containing sulphuric acid of a particular strength, were maintained at a constant temperature of 34° in an electrically regulated thermostat.

The method of saturation with water vapour was similar to that followed by Puri, Crowther and Keen (*loc. cit.*). About 5 g. portions of each gel were used for each set of experiment, the gel being transferred from a more humid atmosphere to that of next lower humidity. The amount of moisture retained by these gels was determined by igniting the gel after the constant weight had been reached in the lowest humid atmosphere. Generally 72 hours were sufficient to reach the equilibrium at a given vapour pressure.

TABLE Ia.

Water absorption.

The cation with which the gel has been saturated.	H ₂ O (in g.) per g. of the ignited oxide at 34° over								
	23.0% acid. V.P. = 33.625 mm.	55.8% acid. V.P. = 10.25 mm.	81.1% acid. V.P. = 0.55 mm.	23.0% acid. V.P. = 33.625 mm.	55.8% acid. V.P. = 10.25 mm.	81.1% acid. V.P. = 0.55 mm.	23.0% acid. V.P. = 33.625 mm.	55.8% acid. V.P. = 10.25 mm.	81.1% acid. V.P. = 0.55 mm.
	SiO ₂			Al ₂ O ₃			Fe ₂ O ₃		
Na	0.3852	0.1672	0.0710	0.5541	0.5167	0.4611	0.2261	0.1630	0.0910
K	0.3395	0.1273	0.0415	0.5300	0.4950	0.4412	0.1678	0.0990	0.0421
Ca	0.4726	0.1428	0.0312	0.5320	0.4990	0.4360	0.1665	0.1080	0.0532
Mg.	0.4174	0.1543	0.0512	0.5250	0.4980	0.4392	0.2513	0.1586	0.0715

TABLE Ib.

Sample taken.	Substituted cation.	H ₂ O per g. of the ignited mixture at 34°.				
		23% acid. V.P. = 33.625 mm.	42% acid. V.P. = 21.357 mm.	55.9% acid. V.P. = 10.25 mm.	62.2% acid. V.P. = 6.20 mm.	81.1% acid. V.P. = 0.35 mm.
SiO ₂ -Al ₂ O ₃ Mixture (I) $\frac{\text{Mol. SiO}_2}{\text{Mol. Al}_2\text{O}_3} = 4.37$	Na	0.606 g.	0.501 g.	0.343 g.	0.293 g.	0.182 g.
	K	0.635	0.531	0.375	0.334	0.225
	Ca	0.620	0.512	0.357	0.305	0.200
	Mg	0.629	0.523	0.371	0.330	0.239
SiO ₂ -Al ₂ O ₃ Mixture (II) $\frac{\text{Mol. SiO}_2}{\text{Mol. Al}_2\text{O}_3} = 1.33$	Na	0.937	...	0.821	...	0.442
	K	0.709	...	0.626	...	0.284
	Ca	0.743	...	0.648	...	0.284
	Mg	0.666	...	0.560	...	0.276
SiO ₂ -Fe ₂ O ₃ Mixture (III) $\frac{\text{Mol. SiO}_2}{\text{Mol. Fe}_2\text{O}_3} = 3.68$	Na	0.549	0.322	0.219	0.193	0.131
	K	0.589	0.337	0.215	0.189	0.130
	Ca	0.545	0.327	0.220	0.198	0.139
	Mg	0.588	0.331	0.220	0.194	0.134
SiO ₂ -Fe ₂ O ₃ Mixture (IV) $\frac{\text{Mol. SiO}_2}{\text{Mol. Fe}_2\text{O}_3} = 1.04$	Na	0.453	...	0.424	...	0.152
	K	0.461	...	0.435	...	0.161
	Ca	0.488	...	0.463	...	0.191
	Mg	0.501	...	0.474	...	0.192

TABLE II.

Sample taken.	Substituted cation.	H ₂ O per g. of the ignited mixture (calculated from the law of additive mixture).		
		V.P. = 33.62 mm.	V.P. = 10.25 mm.	V.P. = 0.55 mm.
Mixture (I)	Na	0.4301 g.	0.2647 g.	0.1802 g.
	K	0.3905	0.2303	0.1532
	Ca	0.480	0.2425	0.1446
	Mg	0.4453	0.2505	0.1598
Mixture (II)	Na	0.4798	0.3625	0.2594
	K	0.4462	0.3332	0.2653
	Ca	0.5058	0.3423	0.2579
	Mg	0.4776	0.3468	0.2683
Mixture (III)	Na	0.3178	0.1654	0.0794
	K	0.2669	0.1154	0.0417
	Ca	0.3432	0.1282	0.0404
	Mg	0.3470	0.1561	0.0604
Mixture (IV)	Na	0.2706	0.1642	0.0854
	K	0.2159	0.1070	0.0419
	Ca	0.2522	0.1177	0.0470
	Mg	0.2978	0.1574	0.0681

DISCUSSION.

Table I gives the amounts of moisture retained by the different samples at various vapour pressures. A good correlation has often been found between the moisture retention capacity of a soil and the nature of the cation with which it has been saturated. Thus Gedroiz (*Zhur. Opyt. Agron.*, 1914, **15**, 205), Smolik (*Bull. Czechos. Acad. Agric.*, 1930; *Proc. Internat. Soc. Soil Sci.*, *abst.*, 1930, **5**, 159) and Perkin and King (*Soil Sci.*, 1931, **32**, 409) observed that a maximum amount of moisture was retained when Na was the saturating cation. This is to be expected from theoretical considerations as the Na⁺ ion, being heavily hydrated, is most likely to increase the affinity of the gel surface for water vapour. Indications, however, exist in the literature showing that the moisture retention capacity is not simply determined by the nature of the saturating cation. Thus the results of Anderson (*loc. cit.*), Parker and Pate (*loc. cit.*), and Bayer (*loc. cit.*) do not bear out the above characteristic effect of sodium ions regarding moisture retention by soil colloids saturated with them.

The results given in the previous section show that besides the usual effect of the cation, the composition of the gel is an important factor in determining its moisture retention capacity. Na-saturated alumina absorbs more water vapour than the same gel saturated with the cations K, Ca or Mg (*cf.* Tables Ia and Ib). The difference becomes still more marked in mixtures of alumina and silica. In the case of the pure ferric hydroxide gel also maximum moisture retention capacity is observed when Na is the saturating cation. In the case of silica-ferric hydroxide gels, however, the order of the various cations in respect of moisture retention depends in a peculiar manner on the composition of the gel and at a certain composition the order is reversed compared with that obtained in the case of the pure ferric hydroxide gel, *e.g.*, Mg-saturated sample shows the highest moisture retention capacity.

The results also indicate that an important factor in determining the order of the cations regarding the amount of water vapour absorbed is the vapour pressure at which the experiment has been carried out.

It is interesting to note that as silica is added to the sesquioxides, their moisture retention capacity gradually increases, reaches a maximum and again decreases, giving small values of moisture absorption with pure silica. The maximum in case of silica-alumina

mixture is at the gel composition 45% SiO_2 and 55% Al_2O_3 ; the molar ratio of $\text{SiO}_2/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ being 1.4. The composition of $\text{SiO}_2\text{—Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ mixture at its maximum moisture retention capacity is about 35% SiO_2 and 65% Fe_2O_3 . It is curious to note that the ratio $\text{SiO}_2/\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ is also about 1.4.

Another interesting point emerges from these data. The effect of substitution of cations on the various samples is most marked at a certain range of composition of the complex. Thus in case of $\text{SiO}_2\text{—Al}_2\text{O}_3$ mixture, the most marked range is between the ratios 2.6 and 0.5. In case of $\text{SiO}_2\text{—Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ mixture also, the most marked range is between the ratios 2.6 and 0.5.

FIG. 1a.

FIG. 1b.

Curves 1-4 refer respectively to Na, Ca, K, and Mg-saturated materials.

The relation between the vapour pressure and moisture retention capacity of our synthetic materials are shown in Fig 1. In our experiments, the water absorption curve of the gels were obtained up to a vapour pressure limit of 34 mm. The foams of the curves are similar to those of Puri, Crowther and Keen (*loc. cit.*).

FIG. 2a.

Curves 1-4 (SiO_2) refer respectively to K, Na, Mg and Ca-saturated
 " " (Fe_2O_3) " " " K, Ca, Na and Mg "

FIG. 2b.

FIG. 3.

Comparing Table II with Table I, it will be noted that the moisture retention capacity of the mixed silica-sesquioxide gels is far greater than that calculated from the law of mixtures. It is remarkable that the base exchange capacity of silica-sesquioxide gels is also always greater than that calculated from the law of mixtures (*cf.* the previous paper of this series). As the affinity of the surface for a metal ion increases, the moisture retention capacity also increases.

In Fig. 3 are plotted the $\log c - \log p$ curves for mixtures I and III. Considering the equilibrium relationship from the stand point of Freundlich's equation

$$c = Kp^{\frac{1}{n}}$$

one would expect a straight line for the $\log c - \log p$ curve. The figures show that all the points, with the exception of the one at the lowest humidity, lie in a straight line. The divergence at low humidities is apparently due to some moisture being held in chemical combination. It may be noted that the amount of water held by these gels by chemical combination is much smaller than the amount necessary for these gels to exist entirely as H_2SiO_2 , $\text{Al}(\text{OH})_3$, or $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$.

The $\log c - \log p$ curves for the same material substituted with different bases are all parallel. Hence the values of n in the above equation is the same for the same material treated with various bases, being equal to 2.3 and 1.6 for samples I and III respectively. There seems to be no difference in the equilibrium relationship between the same material treated with the different bases. The value of K , however, changes, although very slightly, with the substitution of different bases.

TABLE III.

Mixed gel.	Substituted base.	K.
(I) $\frac{\text{SiO}_2}{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3} = 4.37$	Na	0.112
	K	0.120
	Ca	0.115
	Mg	0.118
(II) $\frac{\text{SiO}_2}{\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3} = 3.68$	Na	0.047
	K	0.048
	Ca	0.047
	Mg	0.048

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